

Domestic Violence Against Men By Women In Punjab: An Empirical Study

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Citation: Dr. Geeta, (2024), Domestic Violence Against Men By Women In Punjab: An Empirical Study, *Educational Administration: Theory and Practice*, 30(1), 1199-1213

Doi: 10.53555/kuey.v30i1.6075

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 07-04- 2024

Accepted: 15-05- 2024

ABSTRACT

The National Crime Records Bureau 2021, highlighted concern towards increasing rates of severe domestic violence against men by their intimate partner in India. In 2021, 33.2% of males committed suicide due to family-related issues, and 4.8% committed suicide due to marital problems. The Lancet Regional Health reported that the suicide rate of males has been 2.5 times higher than women's suicide from 2014 to 2021. The Present study focusing on factors responsible for domestic violence against men by women, particularly in Punjab and suggest mechanism to reduce such abuse on Men with the help of doctrinal and non-doctrinal research methodology. The paper emphasized that men have been found facing significant challenges in accessing justice, human rights, and dignity in society therefore; gender-neutral laws may help in protecting the interest of male against domestic violence by women in Punjab.

Keyword – Misuse of Law, Patriarchal mindset, Intimate violence, Gender-neutral law, Women-centric law

1. Introduction

Domestic violence perpetrated by intimate partners against men has become a serious issue in Punjab. It has been found that 3.2 percent of male faced domestic violence in their married life and 13.9% experienced domestic violence by their partner once in their married life (National Statistics 2022-2023)¹. During the period numerous legislations were enacted for the protection of women in a long-time patriarchal society where males dominated female for a long time. Gradually, it has been found that women started to misuse all the women-centric legislation in one and another way. Recently, Save Indian Family (SIF) a non-governmental organization (NGO) in Chandigarh received 1,774 cases of domestic violence of men by their wives from 22 States². A call was received by an Indian Family (SIF) from 30 years old male for physical assault caused by her 28-years-old wife because he refused to her for visiting the parental home.³ On 24 November 2023, wife punched on the nose of the husband with force that he turned unconscious when he refused the wife for a Dubai tour and not purchasing expensive gift on her birthday. ⁴ Hollywood celebrities, Johnny Depp and Amber

¹ Statistics on Male Victims of Domestic Abuse, available at: [https://mankind.org.uk/statistics/statistics-on-male-victims-of-domestic-abuse/#:~:text=The%20latest%20Office%20for%20National,\(ONS%202022%2F23\)](https://mankind.org.uk/statistics/statistics-on-male-victims-of-domestic-abuse/#:~:text=The%20latest%20Office%20for%20National,(ONS%202022%2F23),), (last visited on May 1, 2024).

² Jagpreet Singh Sandhu, "Chandigarh: 1,774 men called helpline in April, alleged domestic violence, says NGO", *The Indian Express*, 29 April 2020, available at: <https://indianexpress.com/article/cities/chandigarh/chandigarh-1774-men-called-helpline-in-april-alleged-domestic-violence-says-ngo/>, (last visited on May 2, 2024).

³ *Ibid.*

⁴ NDTV New Delhi television Ltd. "Woman Punches Husband To Death For Not Taking Her To Dubai On Birthday" 2023, available at: <https://www.ndtv.com/india-news/woman-punches-husband-to-death-for-not-taking-her-to-dubai-on-birthday-4604492>.

Heard attracted the attention for false allegation of defamation.⁵ In addition to these generally some of wives' force husband to leave their old age parents and commit cruelty to them.⁶

A study by "Save Family Foundation (SFF) and My Nation found" that out of 1650, 98 % urban males have been victims of domestic violence emotionally, physically, economically and sexually in 2022.⁷

But generally, males hesitate to report domestic violence against them to NGOs, police and even to discuss with friends and family for the sake of their family reputation and financial reasons.

In 2016, the misuse of "Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act" was also acknowledged in Rajya Sabha.⁸ In *Arnesh Kumar v State of Bihar*, some guidelines were issued to save the male and family of husband from arbitrary arrest.⁹ Recently, the Bareilly High Court gave a historical judgment for punishing the women for false rape accusation and false testimony against male.¹⁰

Moreover, the National Crime Record Bureau released the crime statistics of 2020 and found that out of 11549, 5520 cases were found false with allegation on husband for cruelty by husband and relatives of husband.¹¹

Over the time, some women have exploited these laws for one and other reasons as result thereto,

Many men committed suicide, deteriorated the health, lost jobs, trust in justice and relationship.

The present study identifies the factors responsible for the domestic violence against men in Punjab, consequences of domestic violence on males, misuse of laws by women and national and international framework for protection of males and tracing why male hesitate to report and discuss these matters to police and friends. The work proposes recommendations to policy makers for the protection of men from domestic violence and for establishing a gender-neutral society.

Research Questions

- What are the core factors responsible for the domestic violence against men by women in Punjab?
- What are the probable reasons behind the hesitation of men in reporting the domestic violence against women in Punjab?
- What are appropriate measures to protect the men against the domestic violence?
- What are the consequences of domestic violence against men by women in Punjab?
- Whether legal framework is available to protect the men from domestic violence in India?
- Whether protection provided for the domestic violence against men by women are adequate for the safeguard the interest of men?

Hypothesis

There is need to protect the interest of men from domestic violence by women in Punjab.

Research Methodology

The present research study is a mixed study (doctrinal or non-doctrinal). The primary data collected through questionnaires survey to identify the reasons for domestic violence against male in Punjab, consequences of domestic violence and why males hesitate to report such matters and how far males have trust in available law

⁵ Times of India, available at: <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/entertainment/english/hollywood/news/johnny-depp-amber-heard-case-final-verdict-jury-rules-in-favor-of-depp/articleshow/91948885.cms>, (last visited on April 26, 2024). (Johnny Depp was found guilty of only one count of defamation, while Amber Heard was found guilty of three counts. Consequently, the jury ordered Amber Heard to pay a substantial sum of \$10.35 million in damages, while Depp was ordered to pay a lesser sum of \$2 million. The trial took place in Virginia, where the jury based their ruling on the evidence presented in court).

⁶ *Supra* note 2 at 1.

⁷ Men Welfare Trust, available at: <https://www.menwelfare.in/resources/submissions/study-domestic-violence-on-men/>, (last visited on April 13, 2024).

⁸ Editorial, "Domestic violence Act misused: Centre", *The Hindu newspaper*, May 12, 2016.

⁹ *Arnesh Kumar v. state of Bihar & others*, AIR 2014 SC 2756. "The guidelines issued by the Supreme Court regarding the arrest of individuals under Section 498-A of the Indian Penal Code emphasize that arrests should be the exception rather than the norm. The court directed the police to follow the principles of Section 41 of the Criminal Procedure Code and provided a 9-point checklist for considering arrests. Magistrates were instructed to assess the need for detention before authorizing it. The decision aims to prevent the misuse of the law while protecting individual rights. Violations of these guidelines could result in legal action against police officers and magistrates".

¹⁰ *Nisha v. State of UP & others*, 2024 Cr. No. 470. "A local court in Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh has recently convicted under section 195 of Indian Penal Code and sentenced a woman to 4 years, 6 months and 8 days imprisonment equating the duration of accused in prison for false testimony and rape accusations on men".

¹¹ Voice for Men India, available at: <https://voiceformenindia.com/ncrb-report-2020-crimes-against-women-cases-registered-v-s-false-conviction-vs-acquittal/>, (last visited on April 15, 2024).

for their protection. The secondary sources, including books, statues, reports, articles, journals and case laws have been utilised for conceptual study. Random sampling with sample size 50 from Advocate, faculty of law, student of law and general public in Jalandhar District of State of Punjab.

Review of literature

Judith Lorber in 'The Social Construction of Gender'¹² (1991) explained that rigid societal norms form the basis of gender construction. The terms 'gender' and 'sex' are often confused with one another, despite being separate concepts. Due to patriarchal patterns, males are perceived as being stronger than females. Prejudices refer to sets of attitudes that are offensive to a particular group of people, while discrimination is the blatant negativity expressed towards an individual based on their identity. Stereotypes and gender-based discrimination exist towards both genders which shaped by social factors and has little, if anything, to do with biological variables. Malik JS Nanda, "A Cross-sectional Study of Gender-Based Violence against Men in the Rural Area of Haryana, India"¹³ (2019) found that men can also become victims of violence by women. The report highlights that 52.4% of men have experienced gender-based violence. Out of 1000 men, 51.5% have faced violence from their wives or intimate partners at least once in their lifetime, and 10.5% experienced it in the last 12 months. Emotional violence was identified as the most common form of spousal violence, accounting for 51.6% of cases, while physical violence accounted for only 6%. Of the physical assaults that occurred, only 10% were severe. In nearly half of the cases, the husband was found to have initiated the physical and emotional violence.

Anshika Awasthi, "An Indian Perspective on Domestic Violence against Men"¹⁴, highlights the fact that men can also be victims of domestic violence in patriarchal societies where it is commonly believed that only women suffer from it. Men can be subjected to physical, mental, sexual, economic, and psychological abuse by women. The author focuses primarily on mental abuse, which includes false accusations, and argues that the Domestic Violence Act is often misused by women for their personal gain. The existence of gender-biased laws is a significant concern.

Navpreet Kaur and Sobha Gulati, "Domestic Violence Against Men in India: A Critical Analysis with Special Reference to Indian Laws"¹⁵ (2024) explained that Discriminatory laws against women worsen the situation. Domestic violence is not limited to any particular gender and men also face abuse without clear legal protection. Domestic abuse discussions are often focused on women, which is not fair. In such cases, divorce is an alternative option under Section 13 of the Hindu Marriage Act, which allows divorce if the petitioner is treated cruelly after marriage. Domestic abuse is generally assumed to be caused by men, but due to changing socio-economic trends, men are also becoming victims of domestic abuse. Men do not report such incidents, making them silent victims. Indian domestic violence laws prioritize women's protection over men, which leads to the false impression that men are only perpetrators and never victims. Violence and its stigma can affect men's ability to participate and contribute to their communities.

Preeti Nayak, in "Domestic Violence against Men in India: A serious Issue"¹⁶ explained the consequences that lead to domestic violence against men which directly impact their life and personal liberty. Domestic violence can cause issues such as suicide, health problems, and negative effects on children. It shed light on the fact that fears of false allegations by their wives are a core reason for regarded concern. She suggested more interactions, interviews, and research are needed on this issue. Campaigns to raise awareness about domestic violence faced by men are required to break the silence and cycle of violence.

Sanjay Deshpande, in his journal "Sociocultural and Legal Aspects of Violence against Men"¹⁷ in 2019, explained that domestic violence is not prevalent to women only men can be victim of domestic violence. the study revealed that 51.5% males experienced violence at the hands of their wives. It was found several crimes were committed against men which drastically impacted on the life of men in the society.

¹² Judith Lorber and Susan A. Farrell, *The Social Construction of Gender*, Sage Publications, Inc. (1991).

¹³ Malik JS Nanda, "A Cross-sectional Study of Gender-Based Violence against Men in the Rural Area of Haryana, India", *Indian Journal Community of Medicine*; 44:35-8 (2019).

¹⁴ Anshika Awasthi, "An Indian Perspective on Domestic Violence against Men" *The Times of India*, available at: <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/readersblog/my-thoughts-on-paper/an-indian-perspective-on-domestic-violence-against-men-50632/>, (last visited on May 15, 2024).

¹⁵ Navpreet Kaur and Sobha Gulati, "Domestic Violence Against Men in India: A Critical Analysis with Special Reference to Indian Laws", *South India Journal of Social Sciences*, vol. 22 No. 1, ISSN No. 0972- 8945, P. 71-81 (2024) available at: <https://journal.sijss.com/index.php/home/article/view/231>, (last visited on May 13, 2024).

¹⁶ Preeti Nayak, Causes and Consequences of Domestic Violence Against Men, "Domestic Violence Against Men in India: A Serious Issue", *Journal of Multi-Disciplinary Legal Research*, Vol.2, Issue No. 1, PP.4, (2021).

¹⁷ Sanjay Deshpande, "Sociocultural and Legal Aspects of Violence against Men", *Journal of Psychosexual Health* 1(3-4)246-249, (2019).

Dr Manzoor Hussain, in “*Social Causes of Domestic Violence: A Study*”¹⁸, demonstrates that lack of understanding between couples, often lead to misunderstandings, arguments and physical abuse. The major causes of domestic violence are extramarital affairs, trust issues and violent behaviour, joint families, economic inequality between men and women, which often contributing factor to domestic violence.

Shalini Shivajirao Ghumare, in “*Domestic Violence -A Curse to a Man in a male-dominated society*”¹⁹, explained that domestic violence against men has been increasing concern and bring out with socioeconomic changes in the society. She demonstrates the comparison of domestic violence against men in different countries such as United states and other countries. There are numerous reasons i.e., male stereotypes, fear to access justice, lack of legal protection and family pressure that contribute where men not reported the domestic violence by their wives.

Barkha Kanwar & Navendu Vijayvergia, in “*Domestic Violence against Men in India*”²⁰ explained that men are considered perpetrators due to general gender stereotypes in patriarchal society. Due to stereotypes, majority of men not ready to report the case and suffered in silence the domestic violence by women.

Seep Gupta, in “*Domestic Violence against Men in India*”²¹ 2020, explained several reasons are supporting that drastic impact on the men to go unreported the domestic violence by women in India. Misuse of laws by women, women-centric laws, interest of family and children are major concerning issue which making the situation worse and wholly responsible for the violation of the rights of men.

Reethamshi Kolipaka, in “*Domestic Violence against men in India*”²², explained that globalization and westernization empowered the women about their rights in recent days. The law against domestic violence in India are women centric and excludes the possibilities that men are harassed by women. In his article, she shed light on the section of 498A of Indian Penal Code, how women misuse these laws for their own benefit and personal glitches. She emphasized that there are many laws misused by women which psychologically affecting the men in the society.

Kimmel M. in “Male Victims of domestic violence: A substantive and methodological research” (2001)²³ explained that domestic violence one of the most serious issues where men silently suffered at the hands of their intimate partners. The patriarchal society has been favorable to women-centric which directly or indirectly violation the principle of equality. Therefore, it is high time to reconsidered the effective measures for the formulation of policies for providing the protection to males in the society.

Ann Silvers in “Abuse of Men by Women: It Happens, It Hurts and It’s Time to Get Real About It”²⁴ (2014) explained that abuse towards men by women is often overlooked and challenged to get justice in the society. The violence may include; verbal, physical, legal, financial, spiritual, psychological, and sexual in nature which experienced by men at the hands of their wives. Moreover, she also addresses the prevent measures to taken into consideration to make the healthy relationship.

Kailash Amesur, in “Men on Domestic Violence: The Other Side of Story”²⁵ (2021) explained that fake cases filed by wives on husbands. the primary purpose of these laws was to protect and safeguard women but nowadays as times changed some women misuse this law against husbands to take revenge and distort the reputation of their husbands and in-laws. it’s high time to acknowledge the need to rethink and amend it accordingly so it won’t be misused.

Mayank Patel, “Domestic Violence against Men in India”²⁶(2022), explained women are independent, educated and recognized their rights by the socio-economic shift of women empowerment in the modern

¹⁸ Dr Manzoor Hussain, “Social Causes of Domestic Violence: A Study”, *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts* (IJCRT), Volume 6, Issue 1 February 2018 | ISSN: 2320-2882, (2018).

¹⁹ Shalini Shivajirao Ghumare, “Domestic Violence- A curse to a Man in a male-dominated Society”, *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts*, Vol. 9, Issue No. 9, PP. 5, (2021).

²⁰ Domestic Violence against men in India, *available at*: <https://vakeelkhaj.com/blogs/f/domestic-violence-against-men-in-india?blogcategory=Law+Blog>, (last visited on November 8, 2023)

²¹ Domestic Violence against men in India, *available at*: <https://blog.ipleaders.in/domestic-violence-men-india/>, (last visited on April 25, 2023).

²² Domestic Violence against men in India, *available at*: <https://www.brainboosterarticles.com/post/domestic-violence-against-men-in-india>, (last visited on April 25, 2023).

²³ Kimmel Michael, “Male Victims of domestic violence: A substantive and methodological research” Gender symmetry, MSW center for women and families, Louisville, KY (2001).

²⁴ Ann Silvers, “Abuse of Men by Women: It Happens, It Hurts and It’s Time to Get Real About It”, Silvers Publications, (2014).

²⁵ Kailash Amesur, “Men on Domestic Violence: The Other Side of Story”, Frateclat Private Limited (Kiwi Books India), (2021).

²⁶ De Sousa, Avinash, “Domestic Violence Against Men: A Lesser Explored Phenomenon”, *Annals of Indian Psychiatry*, 6(1) p 1-3, Jan–Mar 2022.

available at: https://journals.lww.com/aips/fulltext/2022/06010/domestic_violence_against_men__a_lesser_explor ed.1.aspx, (last visited on April 15, 2024).

society. Some wives torture their husband and demand for the nuclear family. So, they blackmail their husbands for imposing the false complaint against them which ultimately led the serious repercussions.

2. Types of Domestic Violence against Male

Domestic violence comprises physical, emotional, sexual, economic, verbal, technical and psychological abuse that detrimentally affects the personal liberty and lives of men which prevalent in society.

2.1. Physical abuse

Physical violence includes bodily injury, harm, slapping, hitting with weapon with the intent to inflicting bodily injury to domestic partner. The Hindustan times reflected that less than 2% of the elderly population had been faced either physical or had been subjected to disrespect and neglect within the family in Punjab.²⁷

2.2. Verbal violence

It encompasses a range of conduct including commenting, taunting, and humiliation by their domestic partners. It is disheartening to note that husbands are often subjected to verbal abuse when they fail to fulfil their spouse's expectations or desires. The impact of this form of abuse on the victim's mental and emotional well-being can be severe and long-lasting.

2.3. Emotional violence

Emotional abuse is a form of domestic violence that involves a pattern of behaviour used by the abuser to control and manipulate their partner, causing harm to their mental and emotional well-being. A study conducted in a rural region of Haryana and revealed that a significant portion (51.6%) of the men has experienced emotional abuse as a secondary form of violence.²⁸

2.4. Sexual violence

In Indian society, the male has been found accused of sexual exploitation of women. The sexual violence includes forceable sexual intercourse, unnatural sexual activities, any medical disorder forced by some women with men. This issue remains a significant public health concern and requires a comprehensive approach to address the root causes and provide support to those affected.²⁹

For instances, four young women, have been accused of abducting a male labourer who works at a leather factory located in Jalandhar city of Punjab. The victim was taken by the women on the pretext of requesting an address. However, instead of helping him, he was subjected to sexual assault. It is alarming to note that the victim has not filed any police complaint yet, and the reason behind this reluctance is unclear.³⁰

2.5. Economic abuse

²⁷ Bhartesh Singh Thakur, "11% Punjab elderly are abused: study", *The Hindustan times*, Dec. 22, 2013.

²⁸ Malik JS Nanda, "A Cross-sectional Study of Gender-Based Violence against Men in the Rural Area of Haryana, India" *Indian Journal Community of Medicine*; 44:35-8 (2019). available at: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7658679/>, (last visited at April 26, 2023).

²⁹ Domestic violence against men, available at: <https://www.findlaw.com>, (last visited on April 24, 2024).

³⁰ Telangana Today, available at: <https://telanganatoday.com/four-women-allegedly-abduct-man-sexually-abuse-him-in-punjab>, (last visited on April 24, 2024).

It has been particularly common in relationships where the man is financially stable and the woman is not, or where the woman is entirely reliant on her partner.³¹

2.6. Digital Violence

A newer form of domestic violence with technical era has been used in addition to traditional modes. There are different social media tools to exploit and distort the reputation of husband. It has been noticed that wives sometimes share the false information about violence committed on them by husband and family of husband. Recently, Rakhi Sawant shared obscene content of her ex-husband Adil Khan Durrani on social media to defame him.³²

3. Why male hesitate in reporting cases of domestic violence

Generally, it is found that males hesitate in reporting and discussing the cases of domestic violence against them by their wives and intimate partners in India. Male are considered strong and not crying on small issues for masculinity. The cases of domestic violence against male are unreported for (i) they have not faith in the justice delivery system in the presence of women centric laws, (ii) they are afraid of losing the reputation of family in the society, (iii) to save themselves from false cases from wife of dowry demand, cruelty, domestic violence with other charges, (iv) they are afraid of other legal claims like property and maintenances from wife and intimate partner, (v) Prevalence of patriarchal structure.

4. Role of Judiciary in Protecting Male against Abuse

The Indian judiciary played a significant role in protecting the interest of male in domestic violence cases. Indian judiciary have highlighted instances of adopting a gender-neutral approach while interpreting laws relating to domestic violence against men by women. The apex court recognized the male as victims of domestic violence and secured the all individuals from domestic violence regardless of gender.

In 2023, in *Alok Bharti v/s Jyoti Raj*³³, *Ravindra Pratap v/s Asha Rani*³⁴, *C. Sivakumar v/s A Srividhya*³⁵, *Shikhar Dhawan case*³⁶, *Dhananjay Mohan Zombade*³⁷ High Courts of different states came for the rescue of men and grant divorce to husband on the allegation of mental cruelty by wife.

In 2022, *Vijayalaxmi case*³⁸ Karnataka High observed that husband may seek the divorce on false accusation of impotency without any legal evidence and accepted as mental cruelty on husband. In *Adil Khan Durani case*³⁹, the Bombay High Court punished Rakhi Sawant for dissemination of obscene content of husband without his consent on social media.

³¹ Kumar, A. (2012), "Domestic violence against men in India: A perspective", *Journal of Human Behaviour in the Social Environment*, 22(3), 290–296, available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10911359.2012.655988>, (last visited on April 24, 2024).

³² The Economic times of India, available at: <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/topic/adil-khan-durrani>, (last visited on April 25, 2024).

³³ *Alok Bharti v. Jyoti Raj*, 18 December 2023 Appeal No. 205 of 2023 "The Patna High Court observed that false accusation laid down by wife against husband engaged in extramarital affairs as considered as mental cruelty and ground of divorce under section 13 (1) (i-a) (i-b) of Hindu Marriage Act 1955".

³⁴ *Ravindra Pratap Yadav v. Asha Devi*, 2023 AHC: 106512-DB, "the Allahabad High Court observed that wife does not allow the husband to have sexual intercourse for long without having sufficient reason which is considered as mental cruelty and ground for divorce under section 13 (1) of Hindu Marriage Act, 1955".

³⁵ *C Sivakumar v. A Srividhya*, 2017 2022 SCC Mad 3672, "the Madras High Court observed the action of wife publicly embarrassed her husband by linking him to a female teaching staff member in front of colleagues and students at his workplace as constituted mental cruelty and grant the divorce under section 13 of Hindu Marriage Act, 1955".

³⁶ *Shikhar Dhawan v. Aesha Dhawan*, 2023 SCC online District Court of (Delhi) 24, "the Patiala house Courts granted the divorces to Shikhar Dhawan from his wife on the ground of mental cruelty. The court found Dhawan's allegations against his wife to be true and granted the visiting rights to his son but not express any opinions on permanent custody".

³⁷ *Dhananjay Mohan Zombade v. Prachi Dhananjay Zombade*, 2023 BHC, "the single judge Justice RM Joshi of Bombay High Court quashed proceeding and expressed worry about the increasing trend of separated wives exploiting the regulations of the Protection of women from Domestic violence Act to torment not only their husband but also their extended family members. The court further has been found the three accused as per the contentions by of domestic violence on women not lived together in same roof, they found to lived in three different locations".

³⁸ *Shashidhar S/o Irappa Chachadi v. Vijaylaxmi W/o Shashidhar Chachdi*, 31 May 2022, KHC, "The Karnataka High Court division bench has granted divorce for wife's false accusation of impotency. The court ruled that "labelling a husband impotent without legal evidences is itself a mental cruelty and granted divorce under section 13 (1) (ia) of Hindu Marriage Act, 1955".

³⁹ Times of India, available at: <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/tv/news/hindi/rakhi-sawant-to-be-arrested-due-to-ex-husband-adil-khan-durrani-allegation-supreme-court-issues-a-notice/articleshow/109508270.cms>, (last visited on April 13, 2024).

5. Domestic Violence against Men by Women in Punjab: Data Collection & Findings

Figure No. 1 Age of respondents

Fig.1 reflected that out of 50 respondents, 52% respondent found between the age 18-25, 36% respondents between 26-35 age group, followed by 8% between 36-45 and 2% between 46-55 and 66-76 age .

Figure No. 2 Marital status of respondents

Fig. 2 reflected the marital status of respondents. Out of 50 respondents, 72% of respondents are unmarried, 26% are married and 2% are belonging to live-in relationship.

Figure No. 3: Qualification status of respondent

Fig. 3 represented that out of 50 responses, 44% respondents were graduate, 36% respondents post- graduate followed by 8% doctorate and metrics and 2% with elementary education and post-doctorate.

Figure No. 4: According to you, which factors are responsible for increasing cases of domestic violence against men in Punjab?

Fig. 4. highlighted factors responsible for increasing cases of domestic violence against men in Punjab. The majority of 52% respondents found women centric laws, changing pattern of society, financial independence of women and extra-marital affairs have been responsible for domestic violence against men in Punjab. 24% accepted women centric laws, 8% believed extra-marital affairs, 6% changing pattern of society and financial independence of women and 4% believed financial independence of women have been factors responsible for domestic violence against men in Punjab.

Figure No. 5: Have you ever been victim of domestic violence by women?

Fig 5. demonstrated that out of 50 responses, 14% respondents have been experienced or victim of domestic violence and 8% respondents have not confident with this regard either they have been victim of violence or not. 66% denied for victimization.

Figure No. 6: If, yes have been victim of domestic violence by women, have you reported the case to.....?

Fig. 6 represented the instance of reporting of domestic violence by Men. Out of 50 only 30 responses received and out of 30, 53.3% never discussed their abuse with others, 30% disclosed about their abuse to their friends, 10% with family and only 6.7% reported to police about the instances of domestic violence against them.

Figure No. 7: According to you, what are probable reasons behind the hesitation of men in reporting the domestic violence against women?

Fig. 7 depicts the probable reasons behind the hesitation of men in reporting the domestic violence cases to their peers, family, and police. Out of 50 responses, the majority of i.e., 50% found gender stereotype society, fear to lose of reputation, women centric laws, lack of faith in justice delivery, lack of gender specific laws one of the reasons for not disclosing the abuse cases to anyone, 16% accepting that lack of faith in justice delivery system, 12% found fear to lose of reputation, 10% gender stereotype society and 4% women centric laws as one of the reasons for not disclosing about their abuse to anyone.

Figure No. 8: what are appropriate methods in your opinion to protect the men against domestic violence?

Fig. 8 reflected appropriate methods which may help in protecting the men against domestic violence. Out of 50 responses, 50% found that enacting gender-neutral laws, amending the existing laws by incorporating gender-neutral provisions, reporting the abusive behaviour to police and family members and establishing gender equality norms in the society by changing the mindset of the society through the governmental and non-governmental organisation may help in protecting the men against domestic violence. 22% accepted that only establishing gender equality in society by changing the mindset of the society through governmental and non-governmental organisation, 20% enacting gender neutral laws, 4% by reporting the behaviour to police and family and 2% accepted that by amending the existing laws incorporating gender-neutral provisions may help the men in the domestic violence cases.

Figure No. 9: According to you what are probable consequences of domestic violence against men?

Fig. 9 shows the probable consequences of domestic violence against men. Out of 50 responses, 58% accepted that commission of suicide, mental health issue, physical issue, lose self-confidence, loss of employment, loss of trust in relationship, violation of human rights have been consequences of such abuse. 20% believed that it is a violation of human rights, 10% agreed that these abuse causes mental health issue, 6% found such abuse become one of reasons for loss of trust in relationship, 4% become the reasons for loss self-confidence and 2% accepted this abuse as one of the reasons for physical issues in male.

Figure No. 10: According to you, whether legal provisions are available to protect the men from domestic violence in India?

Fig. 10 reflected that out of 50 responses, the majority of 62% respondents denied for adequacy of available legal provisions for protecting the men against domestic violence by women, 20% found the legal provisions adequate and 18% respondents found not confident about the fact.

Figure No. 11: According to your opinion, do you believe that judiciary play a pivotal role to protect the men from domestic violence?

Fig. 11 demonstrated that Out of 50 responses, 32% accepted that the Indian judiciary played as important role in protecting the males from domestic violence by women and 20% denied the role of judiciary in protecting male from domestic violence against male. However, 48% majority are not confident that judiciary played important role in protecting male from domestic violence.

6. Discussion

The research has been conducted in the State of Punjab regarding domestic violence against men by women. A maximum of people accepted that there has been an increase in the instances of domestic violence against males violating human rights directly affecting their life and personal liberty guaranteed by the Constitution of India. Various factors viz., women-centric laws, changing patterns of society, financial independence of women, and extra-marital affairs have been responsible for increasing domestic violence against men by women in Punjab by 52 per cent of the targeted population. However, presence of women centric laws found another factor (24 percent) followed by extra marital affairs (8 %) as one of the factor for such violence against the male (Fig.4). Male hesitate to disclose and discuss about domestic violence only 14 percent male accepted that they have been victim of such acts (Fig.5) for gender stereotype society, fear to lose of reputation, presence of women centric laws, lack of faith in justice delivery, lack of gender specific laws (50 percent) and some males (16%) made not prefer to disclose for lack of faith in justice delivery system (Fig.7). Generally males (58 percent) who have been victims of domestic violence lose trust in relationship, self-confidence, lose employment, faced mental and physical health issues and sometimes committed suicide (Fig. 8). Existing legal provisions have not been adequate to protect the male from such violence (62 percent) shown in Fig. 10. However, some time Indian judiciary come forwards for the rescue of male from such cases Fig 11. Hence, the study shows the need for enactment of gender natural legislation and changing the mindset of society with amendments in existing laws for bringing equality for males in society.

7. Conclusion

Domestic violence against men by women is a matter of great concern in India. Sadly, a majority of males are unable to receive justice due to the prevalence of women-centric laws. There has been an absence of express provisions or specific laws to protect males from domestic violence. The supreme law of the land i.e., the Constitution of India contained the preamble which ensures the "Equality in Status" and "Equality of Justice". Similarly, Article 14 & 15 guaranteed equality and prohibited discrimination based on gender reflecting the Indian Constitution as gender-neutral document but, the Indian Penal Code excluded women as preparators. Unfortunately, males have lost trust in justice delivery. Therefore, in the submission enactment of gender-neutral legislations and use of terms i.e., "they", "anyone", "anyone", and "whoever" required to be inserted the available legislations, the establishment of National Commission for Male on the line of women may help in controlling the misuse of laws by women. Further, the establishment of support services specifically tailored to help the male victim of domestic violence through counselling services, support groups, legal resources, and free legal aid for male victims with collaborative efforts of government and NGOs may help in promoting healthy relationships in society and establishing equality in the country.

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Annexure 1 (Questionnaires)

1. Mention your age?

- 18-25
- 26-35
- 36-45
- 46-55
- 56-65
- 66-76

2. what is your marital status?

- Married
- Unmarried
- live-in relationship

3. What is your Qualification status?

- Elementary education
- Metrics
- Graduation
- Post-graduation
- Doctorate
- Post-doctorate

4. According to you, which factors are responsible for increasing cases of domestic violence against men in Punjab?

- Women centric laws
- Changing pattern of society
- Financial independence of women
- Extra-marital affairs
- All of above
- Any other in your opinion

5. Have you ever been victim of domestic violence by women?

- Yes
- No
- Maybe
- not applicable

6. If yes, have you reported the case to....?

- Police
- Family members
- Discussed with friends
- Never discussed with others

7. According to you, what are probable reasons behind the hesitation of men in reporting the domestic violence against them?

- Gender stereotype society

- Fear to Lose of reputation
- Women centric laws
- Lack of faith in justice deliver system
- Lack of gender specific laws
- All of above
- Any other

8. What are appropriate methods in your opinion to protect the men against domestic violence?

- By enacting gender-neutral laws
- By amending the existing laws by incorporating gender-neutral provisions
- By reporting the abusive behaviour to police and family
- Establishing gender equality in society by changing the mindset of the society through governmental and non- governmental initiatives.
- all of above
- any other (if any)

9. According to you what are probable consequences of domestic violence against men?

- Commission of Suicide
- Mental health issue
- Physical issue
- Lose self-confidence
- Loss of employment
- Loss of trust in relationship
- Violation of human right
- All of above
- Any other (if any)

10. According to you, whether Legal Provisions are available to protect the men from Domestic violence in India?

- Yes
- No
- Maybe

11. According to your opinion, do you believe that Judiciary play a pivotal role to protect the men from domestic violence?

- Maybe
- Yes
- No

12. Please give your views on how Men's Interest may be protected from the domestic violence against Men?